

TECHNOLOGY FOR TEACHING ELEMENTARY STUDENTS TO THINK CRITICALLY

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Abstract. This article provides extensive information on the technology of teaching elementary students to think critically, the concept of critical thinking, the effectiveness of critical thinking, and scholars, educators who have studied critical thinking issues, as well as teaching students to think critically and the pros and cons of that thinking.

Keywords: criticism, thinking, critical thinking, independent thinking, creative thinking, thinking.

ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ ОБУЧЕНИЯ МЛАДШИХ ШКОЛЬНИКОВ КРИТИЧЕСКОМУ МЫШЛЕНИЮ

Аннотация. В данной статье представлена обширная информация о технологии обучения учащихся начальных классов критическому мышлению, о понятии критического мышления, эффективности критического мышления, а также об ученых, педагогах, изучавших вопросы критического мышления, а также об обучении учащихся критическому мышлению и плюсы и минусы такого мышления.

Ключевые слова: критика, мышление, критическое мышление, самостоятельное мышление, творческое мышление, мышление.

President Of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoyev argues that our young people have independent thinking, high intellectual and spiritual potential and mobilize all the strength and capabilities of our state and society in order to mature, be happy and become people who do not empty in any sphere to their peers on a global scale. In vain, in the development strategy of the new Uzbekistan for 2022 - 2026 "...to raise human value and build a nationalistic state through the further development of a free civil society; ensuring spiritual progress and bringing the industry to a new level; approaches to universal problems arising from national interests, etc., have not been designated as a priority.

Our country is taking a worthy place among the number of developed countries, striving for a great future. It is necessary to use the most advanced pedagogical technologies in order to improve the education and efficiency of the growing generation. In primary education, it is advisable to take a lesson based on various methods, taking into account the age characteristics of the student.

Applying methods that teach students to think independently, develop their creative thinking, giving them deep knowledge from the foundations of science is one of the main tasks of modern elementary education. And for the implementation of these tasks, the use of educational technologies, various methods, methods and distributive materials in the organization of creative work of students in elementary school classes is important in the development and maturation of a primary student, the formation of independent thinking skills.

The problems of formation of independent thinking skills of specialists in educational programs of Lifelong learning in the world are relevant in the theory and practice of pedagogy. In the processes of globalization and integration of education in the world, the issue of developing

the professional training of future specialists is defined as one of the urgent tasks. In particular, according to a Social Survey of employers by the Center for Career Services, founded at Harvard University in the United States, 74.8% of participants identified qualities related to creativity and non-standard thinking as an important criterion determining the professional competence of a qualified specialist. A similar survey at the Nanyan University of Technology Business School in Singapore found that 62.5% of employers included the graduate's creativity qualities in the top three in their line of essential qualities.

Criticism – (Latin) - judging skill-assessment, analysis of a phenomenon related to some area of human activity. It consists in finding and discussing mistakes. Criticism-assessment of something, or someone's shortcomings is also considered to be negative thinking about what or someone. It is a system of reasoning that aims to make reasonable conclusions by analyzing things and phenomena in the process of thinking, and it also has a critical evaluation character. That is, it is an analistic thought that has become a criticism. There have been many definitions of critical thinking-including that it is a particular type of thinking that generates conclusions through fact analysis. That is, it is a form of self-directed, self-educated, self-controlled and self-correcting thinking. Its necessary condition is to agree with and apply strict norms of improvement of consciousness. Currently, the role of teaching students – young people in an educational institution that embodies the content of upbringing in the East in the development of our country to independent critical thinking, as noted by the great thinkers of the Middle Ages Khwarazmiy, Farabi, Ibn Sina, as well as promoting that knowledge acquired in the process of this critical thinking has a great.

Criticism is the assessment of something or someone's shortcomings, negative thinking about what or someone. Criticism of others is the desire to match their attitude to the problem being considered with yours. This usually leads to arrogance. Others do not want to accept the opinions of the critic for being brought up in this spirit. Hence, criticism is an encroachment on the information and energy world of others.

In Uzbek, the concept of criticism has acquired a different meaning and is multidimensional. The concept of criticism includes all the mental activity of a person. Critical thinking has several meanings. These concepts represent the stages of development of thinking, the ability to analyze, its attitude to reality.

Critical thinking is a system of reasoning aimed at making reasonable conclusions by analyzing things and phenomena, which has a critical evaluation character. That is, it is analytical thinking that relies on criticism.

So while critical thinking is one of the good ways to find an acceptable solution, it is not advisable to use it all the time. A person should not always consider himself correct. Although it gives pleasure, it leads to the fact that we do not pay attention to other points of view. Critical thinking is also not necessary to make all decisions. It is often better to use elements of creative thinking than critical thinking. Critical thinking is a key part of intellectual activity, which involves students learning to recognize or develop an argument, use evidence to support that argument, draw reasonable conclusions, and use information to solve problems.

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This implies that the following pedagogical conditions must be observed:

- to make decisions about the inclinations to occupy creative activities in the educational population, to form cognitive needs and to ensure an environment of manifestation of independence in the educational process;
- create a favorable opportunity for creative thinking in educators, tolerant perception of various thoughts and ideas expressed by educators and ensuring their activity in the educational process, finding confidence in each educator that he is capable of creative thinking, regularly stimulating their creative activity; individualization of the educational process based on the characteristics, needs and intellectual potential of the educational person;
- the formation of skills for working in individuals, small groups and teams in educators, expanding their creative capabilities, encouraging them to adopt non-standard solutions along with ready-made, standard solutions for solving problems; the selection and implementation of interactive forms of training and techniques that allow the practical reworking and improvement of cognitive knowledge, which is the basis of the development of creative.

Thus, critical thinking technology meets modern educational goals in accordance with the state educational standard:

- general, cultural personal and cognitive development of students, which provides the basis of training.
- provides "learning training" and practical implementation. The technology for the development of critical thinking is aimed at making independent decisions and choosing a direction in the study of the topic. Student youth uses educational psychology advances in the study of critical thinking that students engage in psychic critical thinking in the process of modern didactic reading. The study of critical thinking is only possible when the diversity of ideas and experiences is understood and appreciated by educators. Critical thinking, which accepts the "only correct answer", does not occur in the process. The development of this idea is not an easy task. But there is a certain set of training conditions that contribute to the formation of critical thinkers.

These are:

- giving time and opportunity to take up the experience of critical thinking;
- give the reader-young people a chance to reflect;
- ensuring the activity of young people in educational activities;
- it is considered to instill in themselves a sense of confidence that every student-youth is capable of critical thinking.

It is most important to have the ability to target and motivate one's own critical thinking, the ability to actively manage one's own desires, to appreciate the time each minute is used to improve one's own personality.

Critical thinking has the same negative sides as positive ones. So, while critical thinking is one of the good ways to find an acceptable solution, it is not advisable to use it all the time. Critical thinking is also not necessary to make all decisions. It is also often preferred to use elements of "creative thinking" rather than critical thinking. "Creative thinking", on the other hand, is thinking that aims to create something new with the aim of finding a solution to the problem. Thinking should be the good side of things and aimed at improving them even more. From this point of view, it is possible that "critical thinking" is not even the best way to think. Students should be

taught to find creative sides to the story in any situation. They are sometimes clear, and sometimes hidden under consciousness.

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